

EFFECT OF FUNCTIONALIZATION ON THERMAL CONDUCTIVITIES OF GRAPHENE/EPOXY COMPOSITES

Xi Shen¹, Zhenyu Wang¹, Ying Wu¹, Xiuyi Lin¹, Xu Liu¹, Xinying Sun¹, and Jang-Kyo Kim¹

¹Department of Mechanical and Aerospace Engineering, Hong Kong University of Science and Technology

Clear Water Bay, Kowloon, Hong Kong

Email: xshenaa@ust.hk, web page: <http://www.mae.ust.hk>

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ABSTRACT

The effect of functionalization on thermal conductivities of graphene embedded in epoxy and its composites is studied using molecular dynamics simulations. The surrounding epoxy matrix reduces the thermal conductivity of graphene itself by 50 %, making it less efficient in improving the thermal conductivities of composites. The chemical modifications of graphene with different functional groups much reduce its intrinsic thermal conductivity, while they improve the interface thermal conductance between the functionalized graphene and epoxy. It is revealed that triethylenetetramine (TETA) functionalized graphene oxide (T-GO) is the most efficient in improving the thermal conductivities of composites among a few different graphene with and without functionalization. The covalent bonds and the ability of long chain of TETA to penetrate into the epoxy molecules facilitate the phonon coupling between T-GO and epoxy, which contribute to the enhanced interface thermal conductance and thus the thermal conductivities of the composites.

1 INTRODUCTION

Graphene is a two-dimensional (2D) carbon material with an exceptional thermal conductivity (TC) [1] ranging from 2000 to 5000 W/mK. Such a remarkable TC makes graphene an ideal filler for polymer composites as thermal interface materials (TIMs) [2]. Many efforts [3–7] have been made to explore graphene or its derivatives to improve the TC of epoxy, which is one of the most popular matrix for TIMs. A fraction of graphene can significantly improve the TCs of epoxy, which has never been achieved with even larger amounts of traditional metal fillers, such as silver and nickel. However, the absolute TCs of graphene/epoxy composites are only 1 – 6 W/mK, far below the values expected from the exceptionally high TC of graphene. It is therefore necessary to identify the reasons behind the extremely low efficiency of such a promising filler, so that targeted efforts can be made to fully utilize its inherent properties. Although a suspended graphene sheet delivers an extremely high TC of up to 5000 W/mK, its supported counterparts show only an order of magnitude lower values of ~ 600 W/mK, [8] because of the interactions between graphene and substrates which can significantly scatter phonons in graphene. This suggests that the surrounding epoxy matrix may similarly reduce the high TC of graphene itself, making it less efficient to improve the TCs of composites. Another major phonon scattering source lies at the interface between graphene and matrix, due to their weak interactions. A good interfacial coupling between graphene and the epoxy matrix should therefore be guaranteed so that phonons can transport through the interface without much resistance. [9] Functionalization is a versatile way to achieve this purpose. Graphene oxide (GO) is chemically-functionalized graphene with improved interfacial coupling due to the presence of oxygenated functional groups. [10] Further functionalization of GO with other chemical groups can facilitate the formation of covalent bonds between the functionalized-GO and epoxy, giving rise to enhanced mechanical properties. [11] However, functionalization is found [12] to significantly deteriorate the intrinsically high TC of suspended graphene, but it is unclear as to whether the surrounding epoxy matrix could cause further reductions in TC of GO or functionalized-GO once they are incorporated in a polymer. Herein, we investigate the effect of surrounding matrix on TCs of fillers, including graphene and its functionalized counterparts, and their composites. The interfacial interactions and

phonon transfer between the functionalized graphene and the epoxy matrix are specifically studied using molecular dynamics simulations (MDS).

2 SIMULATION METHODS

2.1 Models

The models of pristine graphene and GO sheets were built similarly to our previous work. [13,14] Several common types of functional groups, including fluorine, amine, and triethylenetetramine (TETA), were attached to the surface of GO sheets, designating them F-GO, A-GO, and T-GO sheets, respectively. The Condensed-phase Optimized Molecular Potentials for Atomistic Simulation Studies (COMPASS) force field [15] was used to simulate inter-atomic interactions for the whole system.

The epoxy model consisted of molecules of diglycidyl ether of bisphenol F (DGEBA) resin and TETA hardener, as shown in Fig. 1. DGEBA and TETA molecules were first packed into a cell with a predefined density of 0.9 g/cm^3 using the Amorphous Cell module of Materials Studio. This simulation cell represented an amorphous mixture of two reactive species prior to crosslinking with an experimental stoichiometric ratio. A single layer of graphene, GO or functionalized GO sheet was then embedded between two such cells to construct the models of composites for nanoscopic thermal transport studies, as shown in Fig. 1. The dimension of the model was $2 \times 7 \times 15 \text{ nm}$ with periodic boundary conditions along all three directions, corresponding to about 5 vol.% of the fillers in composites. The structure was then minimized for 5000 steps followed by a constant pressure and temperature (NPT) run for 500 ps at 500 K to allow for the filler surface to be completely wetted by the polymer molecules. Then, the cross-linking process was initiated using the method described below.

Figure 1. Molecular models of epoxy, hardener and nanocomposites containing graphene with different functionalities.

2.2 Crosslinking of epoxy

Many methods [16–19] have been proposed to construct cross-linked models of epoxies whose properties are in agreement with experiments. In the present study, a common and reliable method [18] was adopted to create epoxy models with a realistic degree of conversion. The crosslinking process began with identifying the available reaction sites in both DGEBA and TETA molecules, i.e., the end carbon atoms (labeled as R1) in DGEBA molecules and nitrogen atoms (labeled as R2) in TETA molecules. Then an initial cutoff distance for chemical reaction was set at 3 \AA . If the distance between any R1 and R2 fell within this cutoff distance, the epoxy ring attached to R1 opened and a new bond was created between R1 and R2. After all available R1 and R2 reacted, the extra hydrogen atoms were removed and partial charges were recalculated. The new structure was subsequently relaxed by energy

minimization, followed by NVT dynamics run to eliminate high internal stresses. The above crosslinking process recurred with an increased cutoff distance by 1 Å until the degree of conversion of the system reached 70 %. The final structure after crosslinking was cooled down to 300 K at a cooling rate of 1 K/ps. It is noted that, for A-GO and T-GO, the amine groups on their surface also participated in the crosslinking process so that covalent bonds were formed between them and epoxy.

2.3 Thermal conductivity and interface thermal conductance

The TCs of the composites were calculated using the reverse non-equilibrium molecular dynamics (RNEMD). The method was widely used [20–22] and only briefly discussed here. The TC, κ , was calculated based on the Fourier law:

$$\kappa = -\frac{J_z}{\nabla T} \quad (1)$$

where J_z is the heat flux along the direction of thermal transport and ∇T is the temperature gradient along the heat flux direction. The whole system was divided into several slabs along the thermal transport direction, and two slabs at two ends were termed ‘hot’ and ‘cold’ slabs. The heat flux was generated by continuously adding a certain amount of energy into the hot slab and extracting the same amount from the cold slab. The simulation was carried out in the constant energy (NVE) ensemble so that the total energy of the system was conserved. A constant temperature gradient, ∇T , was established after the system reached a steady state. The heat flux and temperature gradient after the steady state were used to calculate the TC, according to Eq. 1.

A method simulating the pump-probe transient thermo-reflectance method [23] was used to calculate the interface thermal conductance (ITC) between the filler and matrix. The composite structure was first equilibrated at 300 K. Subsequently, the filler was heated to 500 K for 100 fs using a thermostat. The thermostat was then removed and the composite structure was equilibrated in the constant energy (NVE) ensemble for 200 ps to allow the equilibrium of temperatures of two parts. The temperature difference between the filler and epoxy, Δt , decayed exponentially with the simulation time, t , such that [23]:

$$\Delta t = \Delta t(0)e^{-\frac{t}{\tau}} \quad (2)$$

where $\Delta t(0)$ is the initial temperature difference (200 K) between the filler and epoxy and τ is the decay time constant. The ITC, G , was extracted by the following equation: [23]

$$G = \frac{C}{A\tau} \quad (3)$$

where C is the heat capacity and A is the surface area.

2.4 Phonon vibrational power spectrum (VPS)

The phonon VPS was derived from the discrete Fourier transform of the velocity autocorrelation function by: [14]

$$D(\omega) = \int_0^\tau \langle v(0) \cdot v(t) \rangle \exp(-i\omega t) dt \quad (4)$$

where $D(\omega)$ is the phonon VPS at frequency ω ; $\langle v(0) \cdot v(t) \rangle$ is the correlation function. The velocity is correlated every 2 fs from time origin with a total integration time $\tau=5$ ps.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Validation of models

To validate the models and force field for modelling the TCs of graphene and its composites, the TCs of the constituent materials, epoxy and pristine suspended graphene sheets, were calculated and the results were compared with experimental data in literatures. The TC of epoxy was calculated to be 0.204 W/mK, which agrees well with experiments. [7] The TC of suspended graphene sheet depends on its length [24] due to the long phonon mean free path. A scaling method [14] was therefore adopted

here to extrapolate the TC of graphene on a micrometer scale, so that the data can be directly compared with experiments using micrometer-long samples. The TC of suspended graphene obtained from our simulation was 2260 W/mK, which fell within the range of experiments, 2000 – 5000 W/mK. This means that the models and the force field used here were confirmed to be appropriate to predict the TCs of epoxy and graphene.

3.2 Thermal conductivities of graphene and functionalized graphene embedded in epoxy

Because the surrounding epoxy matrix is considered affecting the phonon transport of fillers resembling the effect of substrate on supported graphene, [25] it is necessary to evaluate the difference in TC between the embedded and suspended graphene sheets in addition to those with and without functionalization. Here, pristine graphene and A-GO were taken for the study of the effect of surrounding epoxy, and Fig. 2a shows the results. The TC of embedded graphene exhibited an apparent length-dependence similar to the suspended one, while the trend of A-GO is less sensitive to length. The difference in TC between the pristine graphene and A-GO became progressively larger with increasing the length, which signifies the advantage of using pristine graphene over its functionalized counterpart in terms of improving the TCs of composites as their lengths increased. However, the difference in TC between the pristine and embedded graphene widened, indicating detrimental effect of surrounding matrix on TCs of graphene as the length increased. The embedded A-GO did not show evident reductions in TC compared to its suspended counterpart. The TCs of both suspended and embedded fillers were extrapolated using the scaling method [14] to estimate the TCs of micrometer-long samples, and the results are shown in Fig. 2b. It is confirmed that the attachment of functional groups reduced the TC of graphene by more than an order of magnitude due to the harmful phonon scattering induced by functional groups. [14] The embedded pristine graphene showed a TC of ~ 1200 W/mK, which is $\sim 50\%$ of that of the suspended one. It is worth noting that all functionalized graphene showed similar TCs regardless of type of functionalization, and were only subtly affected by the presence of surrounding matrix, with only $\sim 10\%$ reduction when embedded. The above findings signify the detrimental influences of surrounding matrix and functional groups on phonon transport in graphene, which are the major reasons for the low efficiency of graphene in improving the TCs of composites.

Figure 2. (a) TCs of graphene and A-GO as a function of length; (b) in-plane TCs of different fillers on micrometer scale.

3.3 Interface thermal conductance between fillers and epoxy

The interface thermal conductance (ITC), a measure of the thermal transport at the graphene/epoxy interface, is another important parameter determining the overall TCs of composites. The pump-probe method was used to evaluate the ITC, and the temperature changes in the graphene/epoxy and GO/epoxy systems are shown in Figs. 3a and b, respectively, as a function of time. The temperatures

of graphene and epoxy reached to the same level in about 150 ps, while those of GO and epoxy took much shorter time, in about 10 ps, to equilibrate. This indicates that the thermal transfer at the GO/epoxy interface was much faster and more efficient than that at the graphene/epoxy interface. The ITC values for graphene with different functionalities calculated according to Eq. 3 are shown in Fig. 3c. A-GO and T-GO both containing amino functional groups presented the highest ITCs with epoxy among the five different systems. The amino functionalization was an effective way to improve the ITC although it deteriorated the TCs of graphene itself.

Figure 3. Temperature change as a function of time in (a) graphene/epoxy and (b) GO/epoxy systems; (c) interface thermal conductance between graphene with different functionalities and epoxy.

The attachment of various functional groups changed the surface chemistry of graphene, leading to different interfacial bonds with epoxy matrix, as shown in Fig. 4a. The interactions between the pristine graphene and epoxy occurred primarily by weak van Der Waals forces and π - π stacking, with a minimum bond distance of ~ 0.35 nm between their molecules. These weak interactions led to rare overlap between the phonon vibrational power spectrum (VPS) of graphene and epoxy, indicating a poor phonon transport across the interface. After functionalization, stronger interactions like hydrogen bonds were formed between the GO and epoxy, while the bond distance was reduced to ~ 0.2 nm. Covalent bonds were formed between the A-GO or T-GO and epoxy, making the interaction strongest among all fillers. The VPS of both GO and A-GO showed increased overlaps with that of epoxy from 1000 to 1800 cm^{-1} , indicating a much better coupling between their phonons. It is worth mentioning here that although both A-GO and T-GO contained amine groups, T-GO exhibited 30 % higher ITC than A-GO (Fig. 3c). To explain this observation, the phonon VPS between the two different fillers and epoxy is compared, as shown in Fig. 4b. Interestingly, the spectrum of T-GO resembled that of epoxy much better than A-GO. This is because the long chains of TETA were able to penetrate into the epoxy, facilitating vibrational coupling between the similar compositions in the functional groups and the matrix. Such improved phonon coupling led to a better ITC of T-GO. To summarize, it is shown that the ITC consistently increased with decreasing bond distance and increasing bonding strength. The highest ITC was achieved by T-GO due to several ameliorating factors, including a strong covalent interfacial bond, a short bond distance and good interfacial phonon coupling benefited from the long chain structure.

Figure 4. (a) Comparison of phonon vibrational power spectrum (VPS) between graphene with different functionalities and epoxy. The schematics show the interfacial bonds between them. (b) Comparison of VPS between two amino-functionalized GOs.

3.4 Thermal conductivities of composites

The abilities of graphene with different functionalities to improve the TCs of composites were characterized along two directions, namely, in-plane and perpendicular to plane directions, as shown in Fig. 5. All the fillers can effectively improve the TCs of epoxy along the filler plane direction. The in-plane TC of the composite containing F-GO was even lower than that containing pristine graphene, because the relatively weak hydrogen bonds between F-GO and epoxy did not warrant the high enough ITC required for compensating the loss in TC of the filler itself due to functionalization. In contrast, however, the covalent bonds between A-GO or T-GO and epoxy provided much-enhanced ITC, leading to much higher TCs of the composites than that made from pristine graphene.

The poor thermal conduction across the interface is a major obstacle to the overall TCs of graphene/polymer composites due to the low ITCs between the fillers and epoxy, which is signified by the even lower TCs of pristine graphene/epoxy composites in the perpendicular-to-plane direction than that of neat epoxy (blue dash line in Fig. 5). While adding F-GO or GO sheets showed a slight improvement, the TCs were still below that of epoxy. It is not until A-GO or T-GO was used as the reinforcement to achieve a significant enhancement in TC beyond that of neat epoxy, again confirming the beneficial contributions by the amino-functional groups.

Figure 5. TCs of epoxy composites containing graphene of different functionalities and 5 vol.% along two different directions. The blue dash line indicates the TC of epoxy.

4 CONCLUSIONS

We investigated the effect of surrounding matrix on TCs of graphene with different functionalities and the epoxy composites made therefrom based on the MDS. The low efficiency of graphene in improving the TCs of epoxy is the consequences of two phonon scattering events: namely, (i) the phonons scatter by the surrounding matrix, causing the reduction in in-plane TC of graphene; and (ii) the interface phonon scattering leads to a low ITC between graphene and epoxy. The pristine graphene sheet surrounded by epoxy showed up to a 50 % reduction in TC compared to its suspended counterpart, making it less efficient within the composites. For functionalized graphene, the surrounding matrix had a negligible effect on their TCs, with only ~10 % reduction when embedded in epoxy, and they showed similar TCs regardless of the types of functional groups. Nevertheless, the pristine graphene presented over an order of magnitude higher TC than those of the functionalized ones, whether in the freestanding or embedded state, mainly because of the detrimental phonon scattering by the functional groups. Although functionalization reduced the in-plane TC of graphene, it enhanced the ITC between graphene and epoxy through better phonon coupling due to stronger interfacial bonds and shorter bond distances. The amino functionalization, TETA in particular, was found to be the most effective among the functional groups studied in improving the ITC through covalent bonds with epoxy. The long chain structure of TETA effectively penetrated into the epoxy matrix and therefore facilitated the vibrational coupling of phonons in addition to that arising from the covalent bonds. The overall outcome is to produce a composite with a higher TC than those containing pristine graphene or GO as fillers.

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